

Open ODISSEI eScience Call 2022

Empowering researchers
in the social sciences
through digital
technology

netherlands

eScience center

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the Open ODISSEI eScience call 2022

This call for proposals supports researchers in the social sciences who expect to benefit from the application or development of digital technologies and research software, but who need additional expertise in applying these methods.

A competitive proposal should:

- address a challenging research problem in the social sciences;
- clearly explain why digital technologies or improved research software is required to solve the stated research problem;
- explain how the research software developed in the envisaged project strengthens, and connects to, other research performed in the ODISSEI community.

Applicants submitting a proposal must be employed at an organization which is a [member of ODISSEI](#). This call follows a lightweight assessment procedure without the possibility of appeal.

1.2 About ODISSEI

ODISSEI (Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations) is the national research infrastructure for the social sciences in the Netherlands. ODISSEI brings together researchers with the necessary data, expertise and resources to conduct ground-breaking research and embrace the computational turn in social enquiry.

Through ODISSEI, researchers have access to large-scale, longitudinal data collections as well as innovative and diverse new forms of data. These can be linked to administrative data at Statistics Netherlands (CBS). Combining data from a wide range of sources enables researchers to answer new, exciting, interdisciplinary research questions and to investigate existing questions in novel ways.

1.3 ODISSEI Facilities

ODISSEI offers several benefits to employees of member organizations. Affiliated researchers can apply for a discount to use services such as [CBS Microdata](#) or the [LISS panel](#). They can also use the [ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer](#) and enlist the support offered by the [Social Data Analytics team \(SoDa\)](#) in solving computational challenges. ODISSEI also supports researchers planning to or using [ASReview](#), a tool that enables screening large amounts of texts (such as scientific abstracts) for a systematic review.

Proposals must indicate which ODISSEI facilities are expected to be used, and how. However, this call does not provide funding for facilities access.

1.4 About the Netherlands eScience Center

The Netherlands eScience Center is the national center for innovative software solutions in academic research. It was established in 2012 as an independent foundation and receives its funding from NWO and SURF. The eScience Center aims to bridge the gap between digital technologies on the one hand and scientific and scholarly inquiry on the other. Its vision is to establish a robust research community, in which all investigators in all domains are able to exploit advanced digital technologies and research software to answer innovative research questions, keeping the Netherlands at the forefront of cutting-edge international research.

The eScience Center employs about sixty Research Software Engineers or RSEs. As experts in digital technologies and methodologies, they may be seen as the equivalents of postdocs, assistant and associate professors, and top-level technicians at universities. In addition to their specific focus on the development of advanced research software, RSEs at the eScience Center will help applicants interpret the results of their research and help make the tools and methods that emerge from the project (re)usable for the wider research community. They will co-author research and methodological publications together with members of the research team. Based at the eScience Center in Amsterdam, RSEs perform their project activities both remotely and at project locations.

1.5 eScience Center expertise

Awarded projects are offered an in-kind investment in expertise in the form of RSEs employed by the eScience Center. In close collaboration with applicants, RSEs will develop and improve the research software best suited to solving the research questions described in the project proposal.

To maximize the added value and impact for applicants, the technological needs and requirements of the project should match the expertise of the eScience Center. Broadly defined, the eScience Center's current areas of expertise include:

- **AI:** machine learning, image processing;
- **Analytics:** big data analytics, text analysis, visualization;
- **Data processing:** databases, real-time data analysis, interoperability and linked data;
- **Computing:** exploitation of hardware accelerators, high performance computing, cloud computing, combining simulations;
- **Software quality:** developing workflow technologies, improving software practices, advancing software sustainability.

For an overview of the eScience Center's expertise areas, see www.esciencecenter.nl/where-we-focus. For an overview of the research software that has been developed and contributed to over the past few years, see software.esciencecenter.nl.

1.6 Open science, reproducibility, and sustainability

Open science is central to ODISSEI and the eScience Center. Open science enables verification, reproducibility and transparency in all phases in the research process, and maximizes the possibility for adoption, reuse and impact of outputs resulting from the projects.

For project proposals, this means that they should adhere to [the Bijzondere voorwaarden Netherlands eScience Center subsidies](#) and [the ODISSEI User Policy](#).

1.7 Available person months

The call makes available in-kind support by allocating the time of RSEs employed by the eScience Center (see Section 1.4) to the project. The eScience Center's in-kind contribution is calculated in 'person months' or PMs of RSE time, where 12 PMs represent 1,536 hours of RSE time available for the duration of the project. The total available budget for 2022 is 15.0 PMs. In this call 5 projects may be awarded, with 3.0 PMs available per project.

1.8 Validity of this call

This call for proposals is valid for proposals submitted before the deadline of **Tuesday 6 September 2022, 14:00:00 CEST**, until the Management Board of ODISSEI and the Directors team of the eScience Center jointly take a final decision, as specified in the assessment procedure.

2 Guidelines for applicants

2.1 Who can apply?

Proposals can be submitted by researchers with employment at an ODISSEI member organization. The list of eligible institutions is available [here](#) (see also Appendix A). Employees of the eScience Center cannot apply.

Each proposal is to be formally submitted by a single named researcher (henceforth the 'lead applicant' or LA). The LA will act as primary contact for the eScience Center.

The LA must furthermore:

- be in possession of a PhD,
- hold a contract at the ODISSEI member organization for at least the duration of the requested project.

The activities of the LA should be integral to the proposed work plan.

The LA may submit only one proposal in that capacity in this call. Moreover, LAs without a prior history of projects awarded under the Open ODISSEI eScience 2021 Call in the capacity of LA, will get preference.

2.2 What can be applied for?

A project may request an in-kind budget of 3 person months (PMs). The project duration will be between 3 and 6 months.

The method of working is collaborative. Research teams include both applicants and RSEs. The RSEs will offer advice and support during the duration of the project to help achieve the desired results. This includes:

- initial brainstorming on suitable technologies,
- advice on designing experiments and formulating research questions,
- technical implementation and testing,
- help with interpreting the results,
- contribution to the digital methodology component in a research paper.

Each project envisages the following deliverables (potentially after finishing the project):

- publication of a research paper and
- a blog post or white paper and
- software or code release.

Both RSEs and research team members should be available for the submission/review process of the research paper after completion of the project itself. Both RSEs and research team members should be mentioned as co-authors of each of the three deliverables.

2.3 When can applications be submitted?

The closing date for the submission of proposals is September 6, 2022, 14:00 (CEST).

2.4 Preparing and submitting an application

- Download the application pack from [the eScience Center website](#).
- Complete the Project proposal template.

Save the proposal as a PDF and submit it via [the EasyChair submission system](#). The submission system will ask for the title of your proposal and the proposal file itself.

2.5 Specific conditions

The specific conditions that are applicable to awarded projects are as follows:

- The same proposal may not have been previously awarded by the eScience Center.
- Awarded projects must start within 3 months after the award date.
- For a collaboration with eScience Center RSEs to be successful, the research data must be available for use from the start. Before accepting a proposal, this data will be inspected to make sure it is ready for use. If you are unsure whether your data is suitable, please contact the eScience Center or/and the SoDA team before applying (see Section 4).
- Researchers funded within this call must follow the open science principles as specified in section 1.6.
- Proposal must be submitted no later than the deadline set in Section 2.3.
- Applications must be completed in English.

3 Call Procedure

The procedure consists of three main steps.

Step 1: Information event and consultancy

Information event

To inform interested applicants of the specific aims of this call for proposals, as well as the role and expertise of eScience Center RSEs, a virtual information event will be organized on **14 June 2022 at 13:00-15:00 CEST**. More information can be found [here](#). For the projects that were granted under the Open ODISSEI eScience 2021 call, see [here](#).

Consultancy prior to submission

Researchers interested in this call are invited to contact the ODISSEI SoDA team to discuss their project ideas and look at the data related to the prospective project (separately or at [SoDa Data Drop-in sessions](#)). Furthermore, all applicants are strongly encouraged to register for an individual one-hour consultancy meeting to discuss the research questions, suitable technological solutions, the viability of the approach, and the match with the expertise of the eScience Center. An eScience Center expert as well as an ODISSEI SoDA team member will attend this meeting. The registration link is available via [the eScience Center website](#).

Step 2: proposal and assessment

Eligibility check

A formal eligibility check will be performed by the eScience Center. This entails verifying that the proposal was submitted in time, adheres to the template provided, and that the applicant indeed is employed by an ODISSEI member organization.

Panel assessment

An assessment panel consisting of experts from the Social Sciences, ODISSEI and the eScience Center will assess the proposals. The assessment will be based on the following criteria:

Academic quality (34%)

- The proposed research should be novel and aim to solve a specific, urgent question.

Application of eScience expertise (33%)

- The proposal must indicate the technological and/or methodological challenges that need to be overcome.
- The proposal must reflect the ability of the RSEs to give the proposed research a boost through digital technologies.

Re-use and sustainability (33%)

- The proposal must indicate which efforts are made to promote the results of the project.
- The proposal must indicate how the technology and software are expected to find use beyond the proposed work itself, after finalization of the project.

Step 3: Awarding decision

The Management Board of ODISSEI and the Directors team of the eScience Center jointly decide on awarding the projects, based on the ranking and recommendations of the assessment panel.

Timetable

14 June 2022	information event
May - August 2022	Consultation meetings with the SoDA team and eScience Center RSEs
6 September 2022, 14:00 CEST	deadline proposal
September 2022	admissibility check, assessment
mid October 2022	applicants informed of final decision.

4 Contact details

For questions about the Netherlands eScience Center, or this call, please contact:

Programme Coordinator Netherlands eScience Center

Tel.: +31 (0)20 460 4770

Email: open-calls@esciencecenter.nl

ODISSEI SoDA team

Email: soda+nlesc@odissei-data.nl

The eScience Center adheres to [NWO's Code for Dealing with Personal Interests](#).

Appendix A – Member organizations

List of ODISSEI members who are eligible for this call (**updated on 1 May 2022**). The up-to-date list of eligible institutions is available [here](#). If you have any doubts, please contact the eScience Center.

Centerdata
Centrum Wiskunde & Informatica (CWI)
CPB Netherlands Bureau for Economic Policy Analysis (CPB)
Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)
De Nederlandsche Bank (DNB)
Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM)
Erasmus University Rotterdam, School of Health Policy & Management (ESHPM)
Erasmus University Rotterdam, School of Social and Behavioural Sciences (ESSB)
Erasmus University Rotterdam, School of Economics (ESE)
International Institute of Social History (IISH)
Leiden University, Faculty of Social Sciences (FSW)
Leiden University, Leiden Law School
Maastricht University, School of Business and Economics (SBE)
Maastricht University, Faculty of Science and Engineering (FSE)
Netherlands eScience Center (NLeSC)
Netherlands Institute for Social Research (SCP)
Netherlands Institute for the Study of Crime and Law Enforcement (NSCR)
Netherlands Interdisciplinary Demographic Institute (NIDI)
Nivel
Open University Netherlands (OU)
PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency (PBL)
Radboud University, Faculty of Social Sciences
Radboud University, Nijmegen School of Management
Statistics Netherlands (CBS)
SURF
Tilburg University, Tilburg Law School (TLS)
Tilburg University, Tilburg School of Catholic Theology (TST)
Tilburg University, Tilburg School of Economics and Management (TiSEM)
Tilburg University, Tilburg School of Humanities (TSH)
Tilburg University, Tilburg School of Social and Behavioral Sciences (TSB)
TU Delft, Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment (ABE)
University of Amsterdam, Faculty of Economics and Business (FEB)
University of Amsterdam, Faculty of Social and Behavioural Sciences
University of Groningen, Faculty of Behavioural and Social Sciences
University of Groningen, Faculty of Economics and Business

University of Twente, Faculty of Behavioural, Management and Social Sciences
Utrecht University, Faculty of Geosciences
Utrecht University, Faculty of Social Sciences
Utrecht University, Faculty of Law, Economics and Governance (REBO)
VU University Amsterdam, Faculty of Behavioural and Movement Sciences
VU University Amsterdam, Faculty of Science
VU University Amsterdam, Faculty of Social Sciences
VU University Amsterdam, School of Business and Economics